

B-DIGEST

ISSN 0975-2617
Impact Factor 4.9

Journal of Commerce & Management
Volume 2 Number 2

February 2018

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- ❖ B-Digest is published bi-annually and is available against subscription of Rs.250/-per annum

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Nagercoil-629001, Kanyakumari District, Tamilnadu, India
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A STUDY ON THE PROBLEMS FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UNORGANISED SECTOR) AT PALAYAMKOTTAI

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs are key persons of any country for promoting economic growth and technological change. They act as an engine of economic growth, job creation and prosperity of the society. Women entrepreneurs were more in small and micro scale business. Family problems, lack of finance, male domination and lack of support are the major problems faced by women entrepreneurs.

Key words: Women entrepreneurs , Unorganised Sectors and problems

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurs are key persons of any country for promoting economic growth and technological change. They act as an engine of economic growth, job creation and prosperity of the society. Hence developing entrepreneurship in the country can help in solving the problems of regional imbalances, unemployment and optimum allocation of resources. The unorganized sector, covers most of the rural labour and substantial part of urban labour. It includes activities carried out by small and family enterprises, partly or wholly with family labour.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

V. Balu (1998) in his article stated that by providing suitable education training and making them more self confident the women entrepreneurship can be developed.

Singla and Syal (1998) have classified the problems being faced by women entrepreneurs at different stages of their entrepreneurial career into three major categories.

i.e.

Problems related to projected formulation.

Problems related to projected implementation

Problems related to project operation.

In order to overcome this problem the authors strongly advocate Group Women Entrepreneurship (GWE).

Garg (2004) in his article entitled, "Women Entrepreneurs: Problems and Prospects" has mentioned that the problems before women are that they lack of entrepreneurial skills. They are gender and culturally rooted. The problems of women entrepreneurs can be easily overcome with professional training imparted to them.

Shanta Kohil Chandra (2012) in her study entitled, "Development of Women Entrepreneurship in India" has made an attempt to analyze the various public policies and programmes which develop the women entrepreneurship in India and the roles and various effects of the programmes.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 AREA OF THE STUDY:

Area of the study for the present project is Palayamkottai. The project was conducted to the study the unit called "**THE PROBLEMS FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UNORGANIZED SECTOR IN PALAYAMKOTTAI**".

3.2 PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The period of study of this project is January 2017-March 2017.

3.3 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Simple random sampling method has been used in this study for selecting the respondents. In this project 109 respondents are selected as the sample. Sample is used for analysis to find out conclusions due to time and cost constraints, the sample consisted of 109 respondents only.

3.4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The salient features of the research methodology

- 1) The study is an exploratory study of women entrepreneurs in unorganized sector.
- 2) In this study area necessitated the use of primary as well as secondary data.
- 3) A sample size of 109 women entrepreneurs with special reference to unorganized sector was chosen for gathering primary data by adopting simple random sampling method.
- 4) For the purpose of collecting primary information, a detailed and questionnaire was prepared based on objectives and nature of the study.
- 5) The secondary data were collected from books, journals, magazines and websites.

3.5 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- 1 The outcome of the study restricted to unorganized sector only.
- 2 The study was limited to Palayamkottai only.
- 3 Due to the time constrain, the researcher has adopted the simple random sampling method.

4 .ANAYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1

Demographic details of sample respondents			
S. No	status	No. of respondents	Percentage
Age			
1	Below 20 years	4	3.8
2	21 years – 30 years	14	12.8
3	31years – 40 years	31	28.4
4	Above 41years	60	55.0
	Total	109	100.0
Community			
1	General	9	8.3
2	Backward	54	49.5
3	Most backward	18	16.5
4	Schedule caste	28	25.7
	Total	109	100.0
Marital Status			
1	Married	84	77.1
2	Unmarried	14	12.8
3	Widow	11	10.1
	Total	109	100.0
Literacy level			
1	Literate	61	56.0
2	Illiterate	48	44.0
	Total	109	100.0
Qualification level			
1	Up to 5 th	13	21.5
2	5 th – 10 th	20	32.8
3	11 th and 12 th	19	31.1
4	UG	5	8.2
5	PG	2	3.2
6	Diploma	2	3.2
	Total	61	100.0
Period of running business			
1	Less than 1 year	7	6.5
2	1 – 5 years	25	22.9
3	5 – 10 years	24	22.0
4	Above 10 years	53	48.6
	Total	109	100.0

Source : Primary data

Above table shows demographic details of sample respondents (109) of their age, community, marital status, literacy level, qualification and period of running business and its percentage. From the table it is evident that 55 percent of sample women entrepreneurs age

group is above 41 years, 49.5 percentage are belong to backward class , 77.1 percent are married, literate are 56 percentage and illiterate are 44 percent. 48.6 percentage of sample women entrepreneurs are running their business more than 10 years.

4.2 Type of business wise classification

Type of business doing by respondents are given below in the table 4.14

TABLE No. 4.2

Type of business

S. No.	Type of business	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Vegetables selling	10	9.2
2	Fish and dried fish selling	7	6.4
3	Beautician	5	4.6
4	Flower selling	14	12.8
5	Tailoring	15	13.8
6	Accessory shop	5	4.6
7	Petty shop	13	11.9
8	Push cart vendors	7	6.4
9	Basket weaving	7	6.4
10	Milk selling	3	2.8
11	Footwear shop	2	1.8
12	Imitation jewelry	2	1.8
13	Grocery shop	8	7.3
14	Saree business	11	10.1
	Total	109	100.0

Source: Primary data

From the above table 4.2 it seems that, 9.2 percent of respondents are Vegetable sellers. 6.4 Percentage of respondents are Fish and dried fish sellers, Push cart vendors and Basket weavers. 4.6 percent of respondents are Beauticians. 12.8 percent of respondents are Flower sellers. 13.8 percent of respondents are Tailors. 4.6 percent of respondents are running Accessory shop. 11.9 percent of respondents are in Petty shop. 1.8 percent of respondents are Milk sellers. 1.8 percent of respondents are running Foot wear shop and imitating jewelry. 7.3

percent of respondents are running Grocery shop. 10.1 percent of respondents are doing saree business.

It is inferred that, 13.8 percent of respondents are Tailors.

Figure 4.1

Source: Primary Data

4.3 Level of encouragement from family

Level of encouragement from family got by respondents are given in the below table no. 4.3

TABLE No. 4.3

Level of encouragement from family

S. No.	Level of encouragement	No. of respondent	Percentage
1	High level	57	52.3
2	Medium level	42	38.5
3	Low level	10	9.2
	Total	109	100.0

SOURCE: Primary data

The above table no. 4.3 shows that, 57 numbers of respondents are get high level of encouragement from their family. 38.5 percent of respondents are get medium level of encouragement from their family. 10 numbers of respondents are get low level of encouragement from their family.

It is inferred that, 57 numbers of respondents are get high level of encouragement from their family.

4.4 List of the problems while running the business

List of problems faced by respondents while running their business are presented in the below table no. 4.4

Table No. 4. 4

Weighted Garrett Ranking

List of the problems while running business

Sl. No.	Reasons	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted Average score	Rank
1	Seasonal work	3286	30.15	VII
2	Lack of mobility	3448	31.63	V
3	Competition	3972	36.44	I
4	Low price	3367	30.89	VI
5	Finance problems	3828	35.12	II
6	Work place	3742	34.33	III
7	Lack of support	3573	32.78	IV
8	Male domination	2854	26.18	VIII

Source: Primary data

From the above Weighted Garrett Ranking, it is derived that, competition secured the first rank with the average of 36.44. Finance problems secured the second rank with the average of 35.12. Work place secured the third rank with the average of 34.78. Lack of support secured the fourth rank with the average of 32.78. Lack of mobility secured the fifth rank with average of 31.63. Low price secured the sixth rank with the average of 30.89. Seasonal work secured the seventh rank with the average of 30.15. Male domination secured the eighth rank with the average of 30.15.

It is cleared that, Competition secure the first rank with the average of 36.44

4.5 Problems faced by women entrepreneurs in unorganized sector

Problems faced by women entrepreneurs in unorganized sector of is given below in table no. 4.5

TABLE 4.5

Weighted Garrett Ranking

Problems faced by women entrepreneurs in unorganized sector

Sl. No.	Problems	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted Average score	Rank
1	More social problems	4246	38.95	V
2	Family problems	6080	55.78	I
3	Male domination	5760	52.84	III
4	Inadequate finance	5800	53.21	II
5	Lack of support	5255	48.21	IV

Source: Primary data

The above Weighted Garrett Ranking, it is obvious that, family problems secured the first rank with the average of 55.78, inadequate finance secured the second rank with the average of 53.21, male domination secured the third rank with average of 52.84, lack of support secured the fourth rank with the average of 48.21, more social problems secured the fifth rank with the average of 38.95.

It is inferred that, family problems secured the first rank by respondents with the average of 55.78.

5.1 FINDING

1. 55.0 per cent of respondents are belonging to above 41 years.
2. 49.5 percent of respondents are belonging to Backward.
3. 77.1 percent of respondents are married.
4. 61 (56.0) percent of respondents are literate.
5. 32.8 percent of respondents are having education at 5th to 10th standard level.
6. 48.6 percent of respondents are doing their business for the period of above 10 years.
7. It is inferred that, 13.8 percent of respondents are Tailors.
8. 70 numbers of respondents are face problems while running their business.
9. Competition secured the first rank with the average of 36.44
10. Family problems secured the first rank by respondents with the average of 55.78.

5.2 CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that, the contribution of women entrepreneurs in the unorganized sector not properly noticed. The problems and difficulties faced by them are unnoticed. Lack of finance, family problems, lack of support and capital investment was the major problems of unorganized sector entrepreneurs. A dual responsibility of women increases their work-family conflict not only in entrepreneurship even also when women are involving in economic activities.

Government should provide proper training and assistance to entrepreneurship to overcome their problems and do their business happily and successfully.

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